

ERGA

EUROPEAN REFERENCE GENOME ATLAS

IT &
Informatics
Standards

ERGA IT and Informatics Standards

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This is designed as a living document, with the aim that it will be updated as appropriate reflecting developments in community and industry standards and recommendations.

A.OVERVIEW

The European Reference Genome Atlas ([ERGA](#)) aims to coordinate the production of reference-quality genomes from European eukaryotic species in a distributed fashion. This involves incorporating expertise and knowledge from a wide range of partners, from sample collection through sequencing, processing, and ultimately sharing of resources openly and systematically. This requires a coordinated effort between all members, particularly in how metadata, data, and research outputs are collected, stored, and publicly shared following the [FAIR](#) principles, and importantly in concordance with related international agreements and regulations. This includes the Nagoya Protocol, which underlines the core principles of access and benefit sharing as established by the [Convention on Biological Diversity](#) (CBD) and [Digital Sequence Information](#) (DSI).

With this in mind, the IT & Infrastructure Committee aims to outline in this document a set of recommendations, best practices, standard operating procedures (SOPs), and infrastructure requirements to facilitate the collection and handling of all data and metadata arising from an ERGA-related project. These standards will outline how resources can be collected, documented, processed, and shared in a way that is understandable, reusable, and compliant with evolving technologies, infrastructures, and regulatory frameworks.

By following these standards, we aim to establish a best-practice model for managing ERGA's data lifecycle, from production systems and archive repositories to analysis pipelines. As a result, cross-project meta-analyses will be supported, compliance with national and international data sharing laws will be made easier, and ERGA's data sharing will be more open and effective.

A1. ACCESS AND SHARING POLICIES

All data, metadata, software, and other documents associated with ERGA projects should be stored, managed, and published according to the [FAIR](#) principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). In particular, no restrictions should be placed on access to genome sequences, raw data, and non-sensitive metadata that should be submitted to an [INSDC](#)-related data repository. Within ERGA, we recommend the use of [ENA](#), the European Nucleotide Archive, for sequencing data depositions. There are exceptions to this rule, particularly where sensitive information must be withheld, such as endangered species locations, permits, and other legal documentation generated as part of the project. In these cases, the FAIR principles still apply, and as such, this information should be accessible to relevant parties whenever necessary. For more general information regarding ERGA's policy of data publishing and sharing, we encourage readers to refer to ERGA's [Open Data Policy](#).

INSDC data repositories do not enforce licenses, however, ERGA recognises that national regulations may, in some cases, impose a licence on the data or metadata created and collected. In such instances, a clear statement indicating these conditions should accompany any submitted data. Particularly when the data is subject to agreements or documents prepared in compliance with the [Nagoya Protocol](#) or other applicable ethical or legal frameworks.

A2. DATA AND METADATA STANDARDS

Data and metadata associated with genomics projects should follow INSDC and community standards. At minimum, publishing raw sequencing data used to generate research outputs and a minimal set of metadata describing collection, transferring, and storing of the biological materials from which the data were derived. These standards can be taxon- and environment-specific and ensure to meet applicable legal requirements (see above). We recommend following those standards established by [Darwin Core](#) and collecting and publishing metadata listed in the [ERGA Sample Manifest](#).

A3. ANALYSIS AND PIPELINES

Given the scale of the project across biological taxa, sequencing methods, expertise, and the computational burden of the tools and software, bioinformatic pipelines will inevitably differ. Wherever possible, workflows used to process, generate, and analyse should be open, version-controlled, and described in a standard workflow language (e.g., [Nextflow](#), [Snakemake](#), [CWL](#)). Any workflows used to process genomic data should be published in an open

repository, such as [WorkflowHub](#), accompanied by a current licence, permitting reuse and adaptation.

A4. PORTAL AND USER SERVICES

To facilitate the tracking of ERGA-associated genome assembly projects, open data portals have been established by members of the research community. Wherever possible, such portals should be used to reduce redundancy and maximise efficiency towards the goal of publishing reference-quality genomes for all eukaryotic life in Europe. At present, sample collection can be tracked via [GoaT](#) or through the public registration of [BioSamples](#). The status of all samples and genomes associated with ERGA or EBP-affiliated projects can be tracked through the open [ERGA Data Portal](#) or [Biodiversity Data Portal](#).

B. BEST PRACTICES AND RECOMMENDED RESOURCES:

B1. ACCESS AND SHARING POLICIES

In general, the data produced as part of ERGA has fewer restrictions than those associated with human genetic resources. Therefore, ERGA's data-sharing policies prioritise openness and align with the [FAIR](#) and [CARE](#) principles as well as the Nagoya protocol. Wherever possible and appropriate, all metadata, sequence data, and related resources should be published in open and accessible repositories. The recommendations below are intended for all ERGA members and collaborating researchers.

B1.1 REPOSITORIES

The production and analysis of genomes for biodiversity result in many types of data and metadata. These include information regarding the biological sample collected, sample vouchers, permits, images, and personal information relating to the individuals involved. Most of these data types can be archived in existing public repositories, such as [ENA](#) and other EMBL-EBI repositories (Table 1), however, some sensitive data should be stored in a secure location where they can be retrieved when appropriate. Whenever possible, metadata submitted to a repository should result in the creation of a persistent identifier, such as an accession number or a digital object identifier ([DOI](#)), for use in referencing and citation. Within ERGA, we recommend using the brokering platform [COPO](#) to ensure standardised submission

of metadata. The COPO platform also stores additional metadata fields that are not submitted to BioSamples or ENA.

Data Types	Repository	URL	Documentation
DNA and RNA sequences	EMBL-EBI ENA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/reads.html
Genome Assembly	EMBL-EBI ENA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/assembly.html
Genome Annotation	EMBL-EBI ENA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/fileprep/assembly.html#flat-file
Genetic polymorphisms	European Variation Archive	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/?Submit-Data
Sample (metadata)	EMBL-EBI Biosamples	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/docs/guides/submit
	COPO	https://copo-project.org/	https://copo-project.org/ebp/
Project	EMBL-EBI Biostudies	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/submit
Images	EMBL-EBI BioImage Archive	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/submit/
Software	ELIXIR bio.tools Zenodo releases and software heritage	https://bio.tools/ https://www.softwareheritage.org/	https://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/quickstart_guide.html https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/swh-model/persistent-identifiers.html
Pipelines and workflows	WorkflowHub	https://workflowhub.eu/	https://about.workflowhub.eu/
Other research outputs	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/communities/erga	https://help.zenodo.org/docs/
Barcodes	EMBL-EBI ENA BOLD	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/ https://boldsystems.org/	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/sequence.html https://bench.boldsystems.org/libhtml_v3/static/BOLD4_Handbook_FinalVersion_Feb2023.pdf

Table 1: Recommended repositories for metadata and data resulting from ERGA-affiliated projects

B1.2. PROJECT TRACKING AND STATUS

To assist other ERGA- and EBP-affiliated projects in monitoring the progress of genome-sequencing projects and, in particular, to avoid over-sequencing of species, we recommend using the Genomes on a Tree ([GoaT](#)) portal. Genome sequencing projects are encouraged to enter the progress of sampling, sequencing, assemblies and publishing of reference genomes from ERGA- or EBP-affiliated projects. To create a project page within GoaT, or if you have questions about existing entries within the portal, please contact [goat\(at\)genomehubs.org](mailto:goat(at)genomehubs.org).

B1.3. SHARING POLICIES AND LICENCES

ERGA follows an “as open as possible, but as closed as necessary” policy. The majority of metadata, sequence data, and resulting research objects should be published through ENA, which operates under the [INSDC open-data policy](#). In general, all data published via ENA are open and free for all to use, with the expectation that the data used are cited, following best scientific practice. For other repositories, we recommend applying the [CC-0](#) or [CC-BY](#) licence to any data submission or publication so that users can freely reuse the material while providing proper attribution. As a general rule, we recommend that teams performing sequencing of genomic material publish the metadata, raw data, and outputs as soon as possible after quality control and processing are complete. This ensures that all ERGA-associated projects comply with the FAIR principles of (meta)data sharing.

C. DATA AND METADATA STANDARDS

C.1. DATA AND METADATA COLLECTION

ERGA brings together vast amounts of data and metadata collected and processed by individuals working across countries, institutes, and infrastructures, sometimes having to comply with different legal and ethical requirements. Within ERGA, we aim to ensure that the data and metadata associated with the initiative are collected, processed, and published in line with the FAIR principles. This ensures that all steps are robust, reproducible, and open to others. The recommendations above explain where information regarding sample collection, sequencing, and bioinformatic processing can be deposited, so that they exist in a permanent repository and receive digital identifiers. The sections below set out the minimum metadata requirements and recommendations for every ERGA project.

Sample Metadata

Rich metadata should be collected to comprehensively describe the samples used in the research project. This should include, in the minimal case: Species name, sex, and age/life stage of the specimen, sampling location and habitat, tissue or body part sampled, and unique identifiers for the sample, for example, tube or well ID. We also highly recommend documenting all individuals and their institutions involved in the collection, processing, preservation, and identification of the sample. Ethics and legal documentation should be uniquely and permanently associated with the sample metadata. We also strongly encourage samples to be biobanked and vouchered. Full information regarding the methods and individuals involved in these processes is to be documented and stored as part of the metadata.

Within ERGA, we recommend following the Standard Operating Practices (SOPs) outlined by the [SSP committee](#), using the ERGA Sample Manifest and Metadata Brokering Portal, COPO. Full details and current versions of these materials can be found on the [COPO website](#) or the [ERGA GitHub space](#).

Laboratory Protocols and SOPs

Documenting the protocols followed to extract genetic material is essential to ensure ERGA-affiliated projects are as robust and reproducible as possible. Protocols should be published in their entirety, with any modifications highlighted in updated versions. Such protocols should be indexable, for example, by DOI, and referenced in the published raw data, research outputs, and any subsequent publications. Platforms such as [protocols.io](#) and [WorkflowHub](#) allow the upload of protocols and SOPs, with versioning and indexing, which can be referenced in publications and data submissions.

Bioinformatic Workflows

Wherever possible, fully containerised workflows used in genome projects should be published in permanent repositories, where they can be indexed and referenced in associated research outputs. These workflows should be hosted in permanent, indexable locations and detail not only the tools and versions but also the individuals involved in developing, testing, and maintaining them. [WorkflowHub](#), [nf-core](#), and [Zenodo](#) all offer such capabilities. Then, any submitted data, research outputs, or publications should link to the respective workflow, authors, and the DOI.

Research Outputs

Within ERGA, the main outputs from projects will be genome assemblies and annotations. These should be published through INSDC in BioProjects linked to the raw sequencing data and metadata held in the BioSample. We recommend creating an “Umbrella” BioProject in ENA

that contains the BioProjects for sequencing data, Genome Assembly, and/or Annotation, and the BioSample. Any other data analysis objects should be similarly published as Analysis objects in ENA, linked to rich metadata objects published as BioSample objects.

Once all items have been published, the Umbrella BioProject should then be added as a “child” to the relevant ERGA BioProject (e.g., ERGA Community Genomes - PRJEB66264, ERGA-CH - PRJEB49197). This increases the visibility of the individual project but also allows for effective metadata collection and analysis by initiatives such as the [ERGA Data Portal](#) or [Biodiversity Portal](#). Once all objects have been created and published in INSDC, the accession IDs should be used for reference in subsequent publications or other research dissemination outputs.

Vouchers

We recommend submitting vouchers to an appropriate national repository (e.g., [GGBN member repositories](#)) and including the voucher IDs when submitting sample metadata. We will supply more specific recommendations in phase II.

Images

We recommend the [Audubon Core](#) standard for multimedia resources, and the [Bioimage Archive](#) for archiving the images and receiving related DOIs.

D. ANALYSIS AND PIPELINES

D.1. IT INFRASTRUCTURE

Large initiatives such as ERGA rely on heavy computing resources, both in terms of storage requirements of the data produced, computational resources required, and the interaction between IT infrastructures. As such, there will be no unified computational model that suits all needs and restrictions.

D.1.1. LOCAL RESOURCES

It is not feasible to expect all IT infrastructures to interact with each other at every stage, but rather to transmit relevant summary data or metadata when pertinent and publish in a central location once projects have reached a “finished” state. Rather than imposing computational restrictions, we aim to set standards regarding the amounts of data one should generate to reach the standards set by ERGA and the EBP in genome projects and recommend tools and bioinformatic workflows that have been found to produce research outputs of the expected quality.

D.1.2. CLOUD RESOURCES

Cloud computing resources may be an appropriate option if local computing resources are not sufficient to meet the needs of an ERGA-affiliated project. [Galaxy](#) offers compute resources for researchers, with several bioinformatic tools and workflows developed by the EBP community ready for deployment, free of charge. Commercial cloud resources are also available from Amazon (AWS), Microsoft (Azure), and Google (GCP). However, they must be purchased on demand and are often more expensive than local computing and storage. These are a reasonable alternative if the demand is short-term and the task is robust and not likely to require iterative testing or parameterisation. Users should always make sure that the chosen platform aligns with the requirements of their institute and national data-protection laws.

D.2. SECURITY (BACKUP)

ENA and other INSDC data repositories already have methods of archiving and backup in place, so once the data are published here, they should be considered secure. However, before the data are submitted, they are vulnerable to data loss. Therefore, we recommend that all sequencing data be backed up in a third-party location as soon as possible. The costs associated with sequencing, as well as the material cost of sampling all biodiversity, mean that it is often not feasible to sequence a species more than once. ERGA is unable to offer archiving or backup solutions as a community, therefore, it is the responsibility of the individual researchers or projects to ensure the data are maintained securely. As a general rule, we recommend publishing data on ENA as soon as sequencing and Quality Control are complete.

D.3. CODE REPOSITORY

If software has been written or developed as part of a project affiliated with ERGA, we strongly recommend that the code and resulting software be published in a public repository, with an open source licence such as [CC-0](#), [CC-BY](#), [GPL-3](#), or [MIT](#), as deemed appropriate by the authors. When software is used in the production of a reference genome or other ERGA-affiliated project, we suggest that the code be versioned and published in a permanent repository, such as Zenodo, so that the work can be easily cited, reused, and further developed by future researchers and initiatives. While popular as a development area, GitHub should not be considered a permanent code archive, but code from GitHub may be archived by other initiatives, such as [Software Heritage](#). Versioning should adhere to [Semantic Versioning](#) with the following interpretation: the “public API” refers to the input parameters and the output data of the workflow, but not its dependencies. Pipelines should also keep a changelog that explains the differences between versions.

D.4. WORKFLOWS

Many, if not all, of the research outputs produced as part of an ERGA project will be the result of multiple tools and steps chained together into a workflow or pipeline. Such workflows cannot be accurately and unambiguously described via text in the methods sections of papers and must now be fully published alongside research outputs. There are many methods of creating machine-readable pipelines, for example, workflow languages such as Snakemake, Nextflow, Common Workflow Language, and Galaxy, which we encourage researchers to use and adopt as part of their normal working practice. Workflows should describe all tools used, including their versions. They should also detail the input data required to run each tool and how the outputs from one step feed into downstream processes. Once written and tested, these workflows should be released and published alongside research outputs or publications. We recommend publishing workflows via [WorkflowHub](#) or [Zenodo](#), detailing all requirements and prerequisites for running a workflow, alongside a full author list of individuals involved in developing and publishing the workflow. Such workflows can then be cited via DOI, which can be generated by both platforms, increasing recognition of the individuals involved and the work they have done.

D.5. CONTAINERISATION

Wherever possible, software and workflows developed as part of ERGA and the EBP should be written and published in a manner that can be deployed by anyone on any computing infrastructure. This is, however, a significant undertaking, and we appreciate that it is not possible to account for all computing environments, architectures, and idiosyncrasies that exist. We strongly recommend containerisation and software containers when publishing tools and workflows. Platforms such as [Singularity](#) and [Docker](#) are widely used by researchers and HPC systems. They can generally be accessed by anyone to install and run software, either directly or via other platforms such as [Apptainer](#). Many tools and software use environments, such as [Conda](#) or [Pip](#), to install tools and dependencies. However, this method of installation and setup is not without its restrictions when migrating between compute setups. A more uniform shift to Containers will allow more researchers to run more tools and assist in the distribution of tasks within ERGA.